

ECONOMICS

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF STUDIES DEFINING THE LEADERSHIP SKILLS OF CHINGGIS KHAN

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Abstract

This study examines how the leadership of Chinggis Khan, who founded the most powerful empire in human history, has been explored in management science. It presents the findings within the scope of identifying Chinggis Khan's leadership skills and learning from them.

Keywords: Chinggis Khan, leadership, leadership skills, frequency, comparison, results.

Introduction

In the process of establishing and strengthening the Great Mongol Empire, Chinggis Khan implemented policies and activities in various fields such as politics, society, economy, trade, governance, law, justice, humanity, family, child protection, military affairs, armed forces, foreign relations, and diplomacy, achieving significant success. Numerous studies have confirmed these achievements. This necessitates an analysis and synthesis of the studies defining Chinggis Khan's leadership skills to highlight their unique features.

Leadership Skills of Chinggis Khan Defined by Foreign Scholars

According to some large corporations, globalization is the number one challenge for business leaders in the 21st century. However, after consolidating the Great Mongol Empire, Chinggis Khan established global peace, fostered mutually beneficial trade, and created a unified market, effectively implementing globalization and fighting for its reinforcement throughout his life.

In today's globalized world, where multinational corporations operate beyond borders, leaders like Chinggis Khan are highly needed. Consequently, his leadership characteristics and skills have become subjects of intense academic study.

In 1980, a Gallup survey conducted by the "Wall Street Journal" among 782 top managers of 282 major corporations in the USA revealed that the top three traits for successful leadership are integrity, ability to get along with people, and industriousness¹. Professor Y. Batsuuri (2016) confirmed through his research that Chinggis Khan exemplified these traits and applied them successfully. Batsuuri also noted that Chinggis constantly sought innovation, creatively utilizing new technologies and foreign experts².

The 1997 book "*Leadership Lessons from Great Genghis Khan*" by Blenheim Partners reported that

English and American marketing scholars began to recognize Chinggis Khan not merely as a conqueror but as an outstanding leader and top-level manager. His leadership methods have been increasingly studied as essential learning for modern businesspeople³.

In 1999, South Korean journalist and researcher Kim Jong Rae compared the powerful Great Mongol Empire founded by Chinggis Khan to the present-day USA, drawing significant conclusions⁴. Similarly, American scholar Jack Weatherford shared his findings in an interview with the *History News Network* in 2016⁵.

In 2007, Professor Mick Yates from Leeds Business School, UK, proposed the "4E's Leadership Framework" based on his research on Chinggis Khan, which includes:

- Envision – Ability to foresee
- Enable – Ability to implement
- Energize – Energy to achieve goals
- Empower – Delegating appropriate authority to subordinates⁶.

This theory marked a new contribution to leadership studies⁷.

In 2012, *Forbes* magazine published an article emphasizing learning leadership skills from Chinggis Khan. It described him as a leader who built the Mongol Empire in the early 1200s, established religious freedom, protected women's rights, implemented sophisticated governance, and won every battle he led. The article highlighted his goal of unifying the world under a single empire⁸ and introduced seven leadership lessons drawn from Jack Weatherford's book *Genghis Khan and the Making of the Modern World*.

The above studies show that modern leadership scholars analyze Chinggis Khan's leadership process, defining leadership qualities and skills that can be applied in business management today.

Table 1.

Leadership Traits and Skills of Chinggis Khan Defined by Foreign Scholars

<u>1997 - Blenheim Partners:</u> Leadership skills and methods of Chinggis Khan	<u>1999 – Kim Jong Rae:</u> Leadership Techniques of Chinggis Khan	<u>2007 - Mike Yates:</u> 4E’s Leadership Framework of Chinggis Khan	<u>2018 - Forbes Magazine:</u> Seven lessons of Chinggis Khan from Weatherford's book
• Open-mindedness	• Practicality	• Envision – Ability to foresee	• Not to control, but to lead
• Speed and Strength	• Speed	• Enable – Ability to implement	• Care for others, not just yourself
• Building a System of Trust within the Team	• Adaptability and Strength	• Energize – Energy to achieve goals	• Be visionary
• New Ideas and Solutions	• System for Replenishing Capability	• Empower – Granting appropriate authority to subordinates	• Believe only in yourself
	• Trust Built on Sharing Hardships and Joys		• Be humble
	• Risk-Taking Attempt		• Avoid excessive luxury
			• Change the world, but do so gradually
<i>Source: Blenheim Partners. (1997). Leadership lessons from Great Genghis Khan.</i>	<i>Source: Kim Jong Rae. (1999). A Millennium of Historical Figures. Ulaanbaatar.</i>	<i>Source: Mick Yates. (2007). 4E’s leadership framework.</i>	<i>Source: Forbes Magazine. 2018.</i>

Source: As developed by the author

The frequency of the leadership skills of Genghis Khan mentioned in these studies was calculated, highlighting traits and skills that were repeated more than twice.

Table 2.

Leadership Traits and Skills of Genghis Khan Frequently Mentioned in the Research of Foreign Scholars

	<i>Trait/Skill Studied Scholars</i>	Blenheim Partners	Kim Jong Rae	Mick Yates	Forbes	Frequency
1	Building trust within the group	3	5	4		4→3
2	Vision	4	–	1	3	4→3
3	Caring for others	4	–	1	3	4→3
4	New ideas and solutions	–	4	2	1	4→3
5	Knowledge and skills	2	2, 3, 4	3	–	4→3
6	Speed and strength	–	5	–	2	4→3
7	Self-confidence	–	6	–	4	4→2
8	Simplicity, openness, humility	1	–	–	5, 6	4→2
9	Empowering subordinates	–	–	4	1	4→2
10	Adaptability	–	3	–	–	4→1
11	Risk-taking attempts	–	6	–	–	4→1
12	Changing the world	–	–	–	7	4→1

Source: As developed by the author

The results presented in the table are represented graphically:

Figure 1. Leadership Traits and Skills of Genghis Khan Frequently Mentioned in the Research of Foreign Scholars

From this, it becomes clear that the most frequently mentioned traits include: vision or goal-setting, the knowledge and skills required to achieve those goals, the ability to generate new ideas and solutions, caring for others, building trust within a team, and the speed and strength needed to accomplish these goals.

The leadership traits of Genghis Khan as defined by local scholars: The works of our respected scholars have contributed specific findings about Genghis Khan's leadership abilities. For example, in his book 'The Art of Leadership of Mongolian Kings and Leaders' (2009), Dr. Professor D. Lkhaashid highlighted five key leadership traits of Genghis Khan⁹. In another example, Dr. Professor H. Purevdagva, in his work 'A

Brief Guide to Genghis Khan's Management' (2004), listed nine leadership traits that developed in him up until the age of 18¹⁰. In addition, academician S. Naran-gel, in 'The Ethics and Religion of Genghis Khan' (2013), outlined 28 ethical traits and behaviors that shaped him¹¹.

In studying the historical events mentioned in the Secret History of the Mongols, English scholar G. Batkhurel (2011) identified 37 traits and skills that he called the 'Secrets of Genghis Khan's Leadership'¹². Likewise, academician T. Dorj, in his work 'The Secret of Genghis Khan's Leadership Wisdom' (2016), defined 10 key traits and abilities¹³. All of these findings are summarized in the table below

Table 3.

Leadership Traits and Skills of Genghis Khan Defined in the Research of Internal Scholars

Scholar	Work	Leadership Traits and Skills of Genghis Khaan
Dr. Profes-sor D. Lkhaa-shid	<i>The Art of Leadership of Mongolian Kings and Leaders</i> (2009)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During difficult times, Genghis Khan's wisdom was clearer than that of others. • He demonstrated the qualities of a leader who is highly sensitive to the spirit of the times. • His leadership art lay in identifying the core of a problem among countless possibilities and making decisions accordingly. • Although advancing and defending were considered the best strategies, he also knew when it was necessary to retreat. • The foundation of Genghis Khan's statecraft and leadership vision was his deep compassion for people — something that should serve as a guiding principle for any leader.
Dr. Profes-sor H. Purevdagva	<i>A Brief Guide to Genghis Khan's Management</i> (2004)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Began developing the psychological readiness needed to become a great future leader. • Experienced firsthand that the peace and well-being of the people are essential. • I have come to realize that true peace cannot be achieved merely by avoiding conflict. • Started developing the ability to realistically sense his surroundings and learned how to compensate for his weaknesses through his environment. • In order to achieve his goals, he learned to suppress past grievances and even collaborate with former enemies as if they were allies. • This was the time when he started mastering the art of winning people's hearts through compassion and fairness. • Became capable of learning from the mistakes of others. • Began carefully listening even to the words of his enemies, drawing intellectual conclusions, and adopting a decision-making style that combined the advice of friends and the council of elders.

Dr. Profes- sor G. Bat- khurel	<i>The Secrets of Genghis Khan's Leader- ship</i> (2012)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor incoming news. • Accept criticism. • Discover your historical role. • Always fulfill promises and be committed to accepting and correcting the truth. • Share hardships and difficulties with others. • Be aware of personal shortcomings. • Be loyal to benefactors and repay their kindness. • Establish strict and firm laws and rules, and ensure they are well communicated. • View everything with clear and rational thinking. • Prepare for war during times of peace and so on - a total of 37 character traits.
Academi- cian S. Naran- gerel	<i>The Ethics and Legal Principles of Genghis Khan</i> (2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li style="width: 50%;">• Justice <li style="width: 50%;">• Compassion and empathy <li style="width: 50%;">• Courage <li style="width: 50%;">• Honor <li style="width: 50%;">• Sense of shame and fear <li style="width: 50%;">• Truth <li style="width: 50%;">• Duty and responsibility <li style="width: 50%;">• Trust <li style="width: 50%;">• Integrity <li style="width: 50%;">• Patience and endurance and so on - a total of 28 character traits.
Academi- cian T. Dorj	<i>The Secrets of Genghis Khan's Leader- ship Science</i> (2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1. Ability to control emotions • 2. Honesty, integrity, and humanity • 3. Courage and decisiveness • 4. Ability to repay kindness and good deeds • 5. Wisdom and skill to develop others • 6. Ability to resolve conflicts • 7. Ability to adapt • 8. Optimistic mindset • 9. Sociability • 10. Charismatic nature

Source: As developed by the author

As before, the leadership skills of Chinggis Khaan that were frequently mentioned in domestic scholars' research were also analyzed and identified.

Table 4.

Characteristics and Skills of Chinggis Khaan's Leadership Most Frequently Mentioned in Domestic Scholars' Research

	<i>Trait/Skill Studied Scholar</i>	Doctor, Professor D. Lkhaa- shid (1999)	Doctor, Professor Kh. Purevdavga (2004)	Doctor, Profes- sorG. Batkhurel (2011)	Academi- cian S. Na- rangerel (2014)	Academi- cian T. Dorj (2016)	Fre- quency
1	Wise	1	8	9	18, 20, 22, 23	5	5→5
2	Empathetic	2	4	21			5→3
3	Collaborates with others		5, 9	5	6	6	5→4
4	Flexible	4	5			7	5→3
5	Strategic foresight	5		3	18	8	5→4
6	Caring for people		2	7	2, 4, 6, 16, 17, 20, 26	2, 4	5→4
7	Resilient spirit		1		1, 10		5→2
8	Attracts others through compassion		2			10	5→2
9	Hiring the best peo- ple	3	4	14		5	5→4
10	Truthfulness			4	1, 8	2	5→3
11	Developing others		4, 7, 8	18		5	5→3

Source: As developed by the author

The results presented in the table are represented graphically:

Figure 2. Characteristics and skills of Genghis Khan's leadership most frequently mentioned in internal scholars' research.

Skills marked in red have the highest frequency, skills marked in blue have a high frequency, skills marked in green have a medium frequency, and skills marked in brown have a low frequency. Skills marked in red and blue will have the highest frequency.

In the figure: the attribute 'Wise' is the most frequently mentioned attribute in all scholars' research,

while 'Strategic thinking', 'Hiring the best', 'Caring for people', and 'Collaborating with others' are attributes with a high frequency.

Comparative results: Now, let's compare the leadership traits and skills of Genghis Khan, which are frequently mentioned in the research of both internal and external scholars.

Table 5.

Comparative Results of the Leadership Traits and Skills of Genghis Khan Frequently Mentioned in the Research of Internal and External Scholars

	Research by foreign scholars	Frequency	Research by domestic scholars	Frequency
1			Intelligent	5→5
2	Building trust within the team	4→3	Collaborating with others	5→4
3	Vision	4→3	Strategic thinking	5→4
4	Caring for others	4→3	Caring for people	5→4
5	Knowledge and skills	4→3	Hiring the best people	5→4
6	New ideas, solutions	4→3		
7	Speed, strength	4→3		
8	Simplicity	4→2		
9	Empowering subordinates	4→2		
10	Self-confidence	4→2		
11			Empathetic	5→3
12			Flexible	5→3
13			Developing others	5→3
14			Truthfulness	5→3
15			Resilient spirit	5→2
16			Attracting others through compassion	5→2

Source: As developed by the author

The results presented in the table are represented graphically:

Figure 3. Comparative results of the characteristics and skills of Chinggis Khan's leadership most frequently mentioned in foreign and domestic scholars' research.

When summarizing the characteristics and skills of Chinggis Khan's leadership most frequently mentioned in foreign and domestic scholars' research: the indicator **"Being intelligent"** appears with the highest frequency. Furthermore, the following attributes show both high frequency and overlap between the two groups:

- **Visionary thinking** (or strategic foresight)
- **Knowledge and competence, new ideas and solutions** (or recruiting the best talent)
- **Caring for others** (or valuing people)
- **Building trust within the team** (or cooperating with others).

Conclusion

From these results, it can be observed that both foreign and domestic scholars generally emphasize, alongside vision and goals, the importance of intellectual (IQ) attributes such as the knowledge, skills, and innovative solutions needed to achieve them. In addition, they highlight emotional (EQ) attributes such as caring for others, collaborating, and building trust within teams, which also show high frequency and overlap. This indicates that emotional intelligence or spirituality in the workplace was a predominant aspect of Chinggis Khan's leadership. Thus, it is reasonable to conclude that Chinggis Khan was a leader of great intellect and spirit.

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